

A simple screening technique for salinity tolerance in rice: germination rate under stress

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Currently available screening procedures for tolerance for salinity in rice have their own limitations (Ponnamperuma 1977, Aslam et al 1993). Hence, an investigation was carried out to develop a low-cost, simple, reliable, and efficient laboratory procedure to screen rice cultivars for this trait. The hypothesis tested was whether cultivar differences in ability to sustain seed viability and show normal germination when presoaked in saline solutions with high concentrations for several days under laboratory condi-

tions are associated with level of salinity tolerance in the field.

A two-factor (cultivar and time of soaking in a saline solution) factorial experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications under laboratory conditions. Ten cultivars with a known reaction to salinity consisting of four tolerant (Pokkali, Nona bokra, At354, and At 401) and six susceptible (Bg450, Bg94-1, Bg350, Bg403, Bg304, and Bg300) varieties were used in the experiment.

Seeds of cultivars with initial germination within the 96–100% range were soaked in a common salt solution with a high concentration—specific electrical conductivity (EC) was as high as 45 dS m⁻¹. Samples of 50 seeds were removed from the salt solution at 0 (control), 3, 6, and 9 d after soaking, thoroughly washed with tap water, and allowed to germinate on wet blotting paper in petri dishes. After 5 d, the percentage of normal seed germination in each petri dish was recorded. The experiment was repeated once again without the 3-d soaking-time treatment. Percentage data were transformed using arcsine transformation before analysis.

In the analyses of variance of both experiments, the two-way interaction effect of cultivar × time of soaking was found to be significant. The interaction effect was thus further studied using response curves plotted with transformed data (Figs. 1 and 2). For all cultivars, seed germination decreased as days of presoaking in saline solution increased. However, the rate of decrease in germination varied among cultivars. Interestingly, germination rates of tolerant cultivars (Pokkali, At354, At401, and Nona bokra) were found to be much higher than those of susceptible cultivars in both experiments. Pokkali had the

Fig. 1. Seed germination rates of 10 rice cultivars with increasing days of seed soaking in saline solution with EC 45 dS m⁻¹ in the first experiment. Bars represent standard error.

highest germination rate within the tolerant group. Thus, Pokkali could be ranked highly tolerant and Nona bokra, At401, and At354 could be ranked tolerant. In the susceptible group, based on the germination rates, Bg450 appeared to be moderately susceptible; Bg94-1, Bg300, Bg403, and Bg350 appeared to be susceptible; and Bg304 appeared to be highly susceptible to salinity. These results are in perfect agreement with the known reactions of these cultivars to salinity in the field. In addition, mean comparisons among cultivars at 6 and 9 d of soaking showed that the 9-d soaking treatment would be the best in clearly identifying cultivars highly tolerant, tolerant, and susceptible to salinity (Figs. 1 and 2). Thus, the proposed laboratory screening procedure appeared simple, effective, reliable, and comparatively less expensive and less cumbersome.

Fig. 2. Seed germination rates of 10 rice cultivars with increasing days of seed soaking in saline solution with EC 45 dS m⁻¹ in the second experiment. Bars represent standard error.

References

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